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Organization of Cultural and Leisure Events on the Basis of Village Cultural Centers

Abstract: *Introduction.* The relevance of the research topic is due to the significant impact of cultural and leisure events on strengthening social cooperation and cooperation between different groups of the rural population, as well as the urgent need to revitalize the cultural development of rural areas in Ukraine. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is theoretical foundations and practical recommendations development for the organization of cultural and leisure events based on rural cultural centers, which will provide an opportunity to increase the effectiveness of their activities in the village. Systematic, interdisciplinary, contextual, participatory, complex, empirical, comparative, and strategic approaches served as the methodological basis of the study. *Results.* The essence of the cultural center as the main focus of the organization of socio-cultural activities in the village is revealed. The role and significance of rural culture centers in culture and leisure development in rural areas are defined. Also we would like to analyze examples of successful organization of cultural and leisure activities based on village cultural centers in different regions of Ukraine. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty of the study consists in deepening the study of various aspects of the organization of cultural and leisure activities based on village cultural centers, their influence on the development of rural areas, and a cultural environment formation. The significance of the study of the organization of cultural leisure based on the village house of culture is manifested in the preservation and expansion of the cultural experience and traditions of the Ukrainian people, the promotion of tourism in rural areas, which can become an important source of income and support for local communities.

Keywords: culture house, village, rural areas, cultural and entertainment events, leisure, organization.

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1. Introduction

The problem formulation. Cultural and leisure events organization based on rural cultural centers is a significant factor in cultural life development in rural settlements. The village cultural center is the main center of the village cultural life, a place where people gather to gain new knowledge, spiritual development, creative realization, recreation, and interaction with other community residents.

The organization of cultural and leisure events based on the village center of culture is of great importance for the development of the village community. These events especially attract the attention of young people to cultural events and contribute to the development of cultural tourism in rural areas.

Recently, there has been a special need to study the issues of organizing cultural and leisure activities based on rural cultural centers because, after the beginning of the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation into Ukraine, a global change in the settlement of the territory of our country took place, a significant number of residents moved to villages for a long time.

In general, the organization of cultural and leisure events based on rural cultural centers can be the biggest step in cultural life development and the improvement of the quality of life of residents of rural settlements.

State study of the problem. Theoretical and methodological aspects of socio-cultural management are highlighted in the works of such scientists as Ya. Martynyshyn, O. Khlystun, O. Kostiuhenko, Ye. Kovalenko, I. Bieletska, N. Kochubey, S. Yaromich (Martynyshyn et al., 2020, 2022; Martynyshyn & Khlystun, 2018, 2019; Martynyshyn & Kostiuhenko, 2018; Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2018; Kovalenko, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022; Bieletska, 2010; Kochubey, 2019; Yaromich, 2006).

The issue of organizing cultural and leisure events is relevant for many scientists. For example, I. Kapustina (2017), in her dissertation, investigated the organization of cultural and leisure activities for preschool children in cultural institutions. Authors of the collective monograph “Cultural and leisure activities in an institutional environment”.

N. Maliuzhko and O. Kolos (2019) consider organizational, pedagogical, and socio-economic aspects of work with cultural and leisure activities. Also, A. Liashenko (2018) considers the problems of organizing cultural and leisure events in museums and galleries in his scientific works.

Scientists such as O. Bakumenko (2019), V. Hutsal (2017, 2019), S. Kudriavtseva (2014), T. Lukashenko (2015), O. Malovana (2021), O. Panasenko (2018), M. Slobodyanuk (2019) and others also studied various aspects of the organization of cultural and leisure events.

The issue of organizing cultural and leisure events based on rural cultural centers is relevant for many scientists. Therefore, the results of the research were summarized in their works. For example, O. Maslii (2018), in his article “Cultural and leisure activities in rural areas as a means of population social adaptation” investigated the role of the village cultural center in cultural and leisure activities development in the village. O. Kondratiuk (2019), in her article “Development of cultural and leisure activities in rural areas of Ukraine: features and problems”, also investigated the role of the village center of culture in the development of cultural and leisure activities in the village. Also, O. Minchenko (2019), in her article “Development of cultural and leisure activities in the village: theory and practice”, investigated the theoretical and practical aspects of the organization of cultural and leisure activities based on the village cultural center.

Unresolved issues. Despite the importance of the research results of previous scientists who dealt with this problem, many questions remained unresolved. In particular, the following issues regarding the organization of cultural and leisure activities in rural cultural centers remain unresolved: the optimal number of these activities to meet the needs of residents in culture and leisure has not been determined; effective methods of attracting the public to participate in the organization and holding of similar events have not been studied; the impact of these measures on the development of agriculture and improving the well-being of local communities has not been sufficiently investigated; effective methods of ensuring the safety of the public and event participants in the conditions of the escalation of the conflict have not been determined; the impact of military operations on cultural and leisure activities in rural cultural centers has not been studied; strategies for organizing events that would take into account the needs of residents for military or moral support have not been developed.

Thus, to improve the organization of cultural and leisure activities in rural houses of culture in the conditions of war, it is necessary to conduct further scientific research on the above-mentioned issues and develop strategies that will take into account the specifics of the military conflict and the needs of the local population.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. The purpose of the article is to develop theoretical foundations and practical recommendations for the organization of cultural and leisure activities based on rural cultural centers, which will provide an opportunity to increase their activities effectiveness.

To achieve the set purpose, it is necessary to solve the following re-search tasks:

- to reveal the essence of the cultural center as the main center of the organization of socio-cultural activities in the village;
- to determine the role and significance of rural houses of culture in the development of culture and leisure in rural areas;
- to analyze examples of successful organization of cultural and leisure activities based on rural houses of culture in different regions of Ukraine.

Methodology and methods. Systemic, interdisciplinary, contextual, participatory, complex, empirical, comparative, and strategic approaches served as the methodological basis of the research. Systematic and interdisciplinary approaches allow taking into account the complex nature of the cultural and leisure environment and its interrelationships with social, economic, and cultural aspects. The contextual approach makes it possible to consider the historical, cultural, and social context in which the cultural and leisure environment in the village develops. The participatory approach reflects the opinions, needs, and expectations of residents, visitors, and rural cultural centers' employees. A comprehensive method includes various areas of the cultural and leisure environment, such as cultural programs, technical equipment, human resources, organizational structures, and others. The empirical approach provides the opportunity to use data collection and analysis methods, such as surveys, interviews, observations, focus groups, case studies, and others. A comparative approach allows you to compare cultural and leisure environments in the countryside and the city to identify similarities and differences. The strategic approach directs the research to the need to develop a strategy for the cultural and leisure environment development in village, which involves ensuring sustainable development and achieving strategic goals.

In the research process, such methods were used as, first of all, the analysis of scientific literature. A review of the literature on the topic of culture and leisure in the village and the work of village cultural centers will help to understand the current state of affairs in this field and determine research directions. Secondly, these are methods of expert evaluations. With their help, you can conduct an expert survey on the organization of culture and leisure in the village and the work of village culture centers. Experts can be specialists in cultural studies, sociology, and management, as well as residents and other interested persons. Third, a survey method is conducted among residents and visitors to rural cultural centers, and finds out their needs and expectations regarding cultural leisure in the countryside. Fourthly, observation of the work of village cultural centers and the holding of cultural and leisure events taking place in the village. This will help collect detailed information about events

organization, their effectiveness, and visitors' satisfaction. Focus groups, case studies – organisation of local residents and visitors to village cultural centres focus groups to discuss needs and ideas for organising cultural and leisure activities.

Information base. The following information was used to conduct a study on the organization of cultural and leisure activities based on rural cultural centers: the Law of Ukraine “On Culture”, Order of the Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine “On approval of the Rules for organizing and holding cultural, mass and sports events”, Strategy for the development of culture and art for 2021-2025, statistical data on rural houses of culture in Ukraine on the official website of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, data information portals and sites about cultural events in Ukraine, (“Culture UA”, “Kyiv Culture”, “Dovzhenko Center”, “Art Arsenal”, “Art Space “Magazine”, “Culture of Lviv”), as well as materials of the author’s observations and research on the practice of organizing cultural-leisure activities based on rural centers of culture in different regions of Ukraine, collected in reviews and interviews with residents and employees of rural culture centers.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The House of Culture as the main center for the organization of socio-cultural activities in the village

A house of culture is an institution that usually belongs to the field of culture and art, where various events for the public are held, such as concerts, exhibitions, theater performances, lectures, seminars, workshops, etc. Houses of culture can be located in cities, towns, or rural areas and can be organized by state or private individuals. Their main task is cultural and artistic heritage promotion and cultural life development in the community.

According to the Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine, as of 2021, there are more than 8,000 cultural institutions in Ukraine. Among them: 3187 libraries; 1221 houses of culture; 584 clubs (including rural ones); 371 Palace of Culture; 234 parks of culture and recreation; 196 museums; 131 theaters; 112 Philharmonic; 86 cinemas (The Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine, 2021).

The number of cultural institutions in rural areas for 2021-2022 by type is presented in *Table 1*.

The organizational structure of a rural cultural center may differ depending on the size and needs of the institution. However, the main functional divisions of the cultural center can be presented in the form of the following *Table 2*.

Table 1. Cultural institutions number in rural areas as of 2021-2022

Institution of culture	Number
Libraries	2213
Buildings of culture	389
Clubs	584
Palaces of Culture	207
Parks of culture	126
Museums	115
Theaters	48
Philharmonic	21
Cinemas	23
Children's music schools	11
Art schools	5

Source: development on the basis of (The Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine, 2021).

Table 2. Organizational structure of the village culture center

Functional subdivisions	Tasks and functions description
Directorate	Management and organization of all activities of the institution
Department of cultural and mass work	Organization and holding of mass cultural events for the residents of the village
Department of artistic self-activity	Organization and holding of events involving amateurs and talented residents of the village
Department of physical education and sports	Organization and holding of sports events and competitions, involvement of the population in physical exercises
Library department	Organizing and ensuring the functioning of the library, conducting cultural, educational and informative events
Department of art	Organization and holding of art exhibitions, concerts, lectures, etc
Department of technical maintenance	Provision of technical support and maintenance of the building, machinery and equipment
Department of finance and accounting	Organization of financial and accounting activities, ensuring control over the use of funds
Department of marketing and advertising	Development and implementation of marketing strategies, planning and control

Source: own development

The specified structure may differ depending on the needs and specifics of the work of the cultural center, but the main functional units will be provided. It is important to note that a small team often works in a village center of culture, where some functions can be performed by one person or several employees from the same department.

3.2. The role of the village house of culture in the development of culture and leisure in rural areas

A significant part, more than 55%, of visitors to cultural and leisure-type institutions, consciously using various channels (not limited to personal empirical acquaintance with cultural and leisure activities), is looking for ways to improve their leisure time to increase their cultural and social potential. This circumstance is becoming more and more important in accelerating the maturation and awareness of the needs in cultural and recreational activities and in the formation of initial proposals for the improvement of modern structures.

Today, cultural centers, clubs, libraries, museums, cinemas, parks of culture and recreation, theater and performance organizations, in addition to the organization of cultural and leisure activities financed from the state budget, provide the population with dozens of types of paid services, many of which were previously free.

The value and effectiveness of a cultural and leisure event in rural areas mostly have no specifics and are determined by general features (Holovach, 2017 p. 24-29), which are listed in *Table 3*.

At the stage of cultural development, the stage of organizational and economic transformations has come. In this cultural and recreational sphere, new ways of solving the issues of the institutions' activities and effective management system development have become necessary. To keep up with the times, it is necessary to rely on an information and analytical basis, sociological information, and monitoring studies of cultural needs and requests of various population groups. Therefore, the intensification of research and analytical support for the activities of cultural and leisure institutions is becoming relevant (Kondratiuk, 2019).

Each cultural institution is designed to become person's favorite place to relax, meet with friends and acquaintances, and spend their leisure time wisely. Only if the population has a permanent interest in cultural and leisure activities will the problem of audiences in cultural institutions be solved. For this, the employees of institutions need to know moods, interests, and people spiritual requests and organize work taking into account their motivated choice of types

and forms of cultural and recreational activities. In relations among people, one should observe tact and approach individually in each case, taking into account the mood and audience requests with a specific situation, that is, creatively. The interests and requests of different age groups of the population differ significantly. Therefore, it is vital to consider the population age characteristics when organizing cultural and leisure activities.

Table 3. General features of cultural and leisure events in the countryside

Signs of a cultural and leisure event	Example
Focus on the development of the cultural identity and traditions of the people	Folklore evenings
Organizing competitions and contests on various topics related to cultural heritage and entertainment	Competition for the best manufacturer of folk crafts
Holding exhibitions of folk art, arts and crafts and other attributes of culture	Exhibition of paintings by local artists
Holding sports competitions and games such as football, volleyball, basketball, tug-of-war, sled races, etc.	Mini-football tournament
Organization of music concerts, folk festivals, dance festivals, discos and other entertainment events	Concert of modern Ukrainian music
Excursions to historical and cultural monuments of the area	Excursion to the museum of local history

Source: own development

In each age, there is a specific potential of leading requests, which must be realized at this time, but not earlier and not later, otherwise, the requests themselves may not manifest. This regularity is especially clearly manifested in the period of childhood, at a young age. It is at this age that the closest social environment, as well as society in general, should create favorable conditions so that representatives of the younger generation can, first of all, master the cultural heritage, folklore, folk games, music, and the most important moral values; secondly, to realize creative potential, as well as innate qualities that determine the constructive development of the individual during the next life. Therefore, in any society, a huge amount of art, games, fun, and entertainment is produced, which are specially designed for the individual development of representatives of the younger generation. The organization of leisure time of young children requires special attention when the need for increased physical activity, cognitive activity, as well as the desire to spend free time with peers for the sake of communication comes to the fore (Honcharova, 2000, p. 19-26). The content, forms, and methods of work among young people should be

thought through especially carefully. The peak needs for communication with peers is among young people aged 15-25. For all the importance and power of socialization of a young person in the educational and industrial team, for all the need for meaningful leisure activities, for all the scale of growth, leisure industry, tourism, sports, library, and club affairs, young people stubbornly “go astray” in the company of their peers. So, communication in a youth company is a form of leisure that a young person needs organically.

Young people make up more than half of the country’s adult population, and youth is the overwhelming majority of visitors to cultural institutions. Therefore, working with youth, children, and teenagers is a very responsible task that requires differentiated, deeply thought-out, highly professional, and interesting work. The activity of cultural institutions among pensioners needs a serious attitude. This is a very appreciative audience. With the correct definition of the content and appropriate methods of work, elderly people can become regular visitors, direct participants, and activists in the preparation and conducted cultural leisure programs and active assistants of specialists of cultural institutions. In many cultural institutions, pensioners are members of public councils, are organizers, and willingly share their rich life experiences with young people.

The underestimation of meaningful and active leisure time among those over 50-60 is being revised today. Representatives of the “third age” (as defined by social workers and demographers) do not always want to spend their free time sitting in front of the TV or relaxing at the summer cottage. Passive leisure is especially uncharacteristic of people who were actively engaged in professional activities before that. After retirement, they cannot drastically change their lives and go to a passive existence, which is limited to the walls of the house. Such people need strong emotions, new impressions, and maintaining a wide range of acquaintances. If we talk about representatives of the middle age groups, organized leisure in any country is aimed at them. At the same time, such social parameters of people’s lives as their place of residence, marital status, nature and level of remuneration, as well as individual preferences in leisure activities are taken into account.

3.3. Examples of cultural and leisure activities events successful organization on the basis of rural houses of culture in different regions of Ukraine

The organization of cultural and leisure events based on the village center of culture is a very important and relevant topic for culture and entertainment development in rural areas of Ukraine.

Based on the conducted research and generalization of data, we will present a table with cultural events that can be held in villages (*Table 4*)

Table 4. Examples of cultural events

Cultural events	Description
Concerts	Musical performances by artists, which can be both professional and amateur
Exhibitions	Shows of paintings, sculptures, photographs, handicrafts, etc.
Festivals	Holding a certain event or thematic event, for example, festivals of music, culture, gastronomy, etc.
Dancing	Dance events that can be organized in different styles and for different age groups
Sports competitions	Competitions in various sports that can be organized for children and adults
Lectures	Presentations and discussions on various topics that can be useful for local residents
Movie screenings	Screenings of films on the big screen, which can be organized for both children and adults

Source: own development

These are just some of the possible cultural events that can take place in the villages. According to the needs and interests of the local population, other types of activities may be held.

Below, we will consider several examples of successful organization of cultural and leisure events based on rural houses of culture in different regions of Ukraine.

“Slobozhanski fun” festival in the Kharkiv region. This festival is held annually in the village of Hannivka based on the local cultural center. During three days, participants can enjoy art performances, concerts, contests, master classes on folk crafts, and much more. The festival is very popular among the residents of the village and nearby settlements.

Concert programs in Zakarpattia region. Many rural centers of culture in Transcarpathia organize concert programs with the participation of local and guest artists. For example, in the village of Baranyntsi, a concert program “The stars are burning above Borzhava” is held annually, where both professional musicians and local amateurs perform.

Festival “My village, my everything” in Chernihiv region. the festival is special, after which it is organized in the countryside to draw attention to the development of agriculture.

Khmelnyskyi region: Shrove Tuesday in Satanov. Every year, the Mas-lenitsa festival is held at the village cultural center in Satanov, which gathers

many residents and tourists. The organizers invite musicians to the event and arrange contests, entertainment, and mask-painting workshops. As a result of this event, the village cultural center becomes a gathering place for people from different cities and villages, and Sataniv earns money from the tourism business.

Volyn Region: “Shorstky-fest” film festival. The village cultural center in the village of Shorstki of the Volodymyr-Volyn district is celebrated by the organization of the annual film festival “Shorstki-fest”. Organizers show films by domestic and foreign directors and organize discussions, workshops, and other events related to cinematography. The film festival gathers many participants from different parts of the country and contributes to tourism development in the region.

Cherkasy region: Pysanka festival. Every year, the “Pysanka” festival takes place at the village center of culture in the village of Korzhivka, Cherkasy district. This is a celebration of the art of Easter egg painting which attracts artists from all over Ukraine.

4. Conclusions

The results of the study made it possible to define the concept of cultural centers, their role in the organization of cultural and leisure activities, and to reach the following conclusions:

1. The article analyzed the peculiarities of the organization of cultural and leisure activities based on the village center of culture, identified problems, and suggested ways to solve them. The study showed a great need to organize cultural and leisure activities in the village, but in this process, it is essential to consider the specific conditions of the territory and the needs of the local population.

2. Based on the analysis of examples of successful practices from different regions of Ukraine, it was determined that an important condition for success is the active participation of the public in the process of planning and implementing cultural and recreational events. In addition, support from the state and local self-government bodies is necessary.

3. The study of the organization of cultural and leisure activities based on the village center of culture has great scientific novelty, as it is aimed at studying the practical aspects of the cultural and leisure environment development in rural areas. As a result of the study, definite trends in the development of culture and leisure in the village were revealed, and ways of their further improvement were proposed.

The scientific novelty. The novelty of the research lies in the deepening of the study of various aspects of the organization of cultural and leisure activities based on rural cultural centers, their influence on the development

of rural areas, and cultural environment formation. In particular, in studying the impact of cultural leisure on rural areas' development and improving the quality of residents' life, in the study of various forms and methods of organizing cultural leisure based on the village house of culture, their influence on the formation of the cultural environment and the improvement of the socio-economic development of rural areas; in the analysis of innovative approaches in conducting cultural leisure based on the village house of culture, the use of modern technologies and information resources to attract the public and organize events; in the study of the social impact of cultural leisure on local communities, their mentality and outlook, which can contribute to the formation of national self-awareness and raising the cultural level of the population.

The significance of the study. The theoretical and practical significance of the study of the organization of cultural leisure based on the village house of culture has three aspects. First, this issue concerns the development of culture in rural settlements, which is significant for preserving and expanding the cultural experience and traditions of the Ukrainian people. Secondly, such measures contribute to tourism development in rural areas, which can become an important source of income and support for local communities. Thirdly, the organization of cultural and leisure activities based on the village center of culture is a central tool for strengthening social cooperation and cooperation between different rural population groups. The research results on this topic can help to identify effective approaches and recommendations for the successful organization of cultural leisure based on the village house of culture and contribute to the development of rural culture in Ukraine as a whole.

Prospects for further research. The study of the organization of cultural leisure based on the village cultural center has significant potential for further research. One of the directions is the study of the impact of cultural and leisure activities on the development of the rural community, as well as their impact on the formation of the social and cultural identity of the residents of rural areas.

It is essentially to study the mechanisms of attracting young people to participate in cultural and leisure activities based on the village center of culture, as well as the development and implementation of effective programs for artistic, cultural, and leisure initiatives development in rural areas. Also, it is important to study the possibilities of using information and communication technologies to increase the effectiveness of cultural and leisure activities organization based on the village house of culture and attract a wider audience to participate in such events.

Therefore, the study of the organization of cultural leisure based on the village house of culture is an actual and promising direction of research that can help solve important problems of the development of rural areas and improve the quality of life of residents of rural communities.

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